

INFLUENCE OF PROLIFERATING CITIZEN JOURNALISM ON CONVENTIONAL MEDIA IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

Israel OGUCHE, PhD

Department of Mass Communication
Faculty of Communication and Media Studies
Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba Kogi State
oguche.israele@gmail.com /+2348069222599

Cordelia Furomkai CLAYTON

Department of Film and Multimedia Studies
Faculty of Communication and Media Studies
Bingham University, Karu, Nasarawa State
cordeliabinauto@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of digital communication technologies and the widespread use of social media platforms have significantly transformed the journalism landscape, giving rise to citizen journalism as an alternative source of news and information dissemination. This study examined the influence of proliferating citizen journalism on conventional media practice in Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated the extent to which citizen journalism influences the news agenda of conventional media, the challenges and opportunities it presents, and its implications for media credibility. The study was anchored on Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory and adopted a survey research design. A census approach was employed, involving the entire population of 186 registered journalists in Kogi State. Out of this number, 181 valid responses were obtained through the administration of structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores and standard deviations, while a hypothesis was tested using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Findings revealed that citizen journalism has become a major force in shaping the news agenda of conventional media, as issues first reported by citizens often attract mainstream media attention. The study further found that citizen journalism presents challenges such as misinformation, ethical concerns, and difficulties in maintaining professional standards. The study concludes that citizen journalism serves as both a challenge and a resource to conventional media practice. It recommends stronger verification mechanisms, strategic collaboration with responsible citizen journalists, and increased digital adaptation by conventional media organizations to sustain credibility, professionalism, and public trust in the evolving media environment.

Keywords: Citizen Journalism, Conventional Media, Media Credibility, News Agenda, Journalism Practice, Information.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of digital communication technologies has transformed the way information is created, distributed, and consumed across the world. The widespread use of smartphones, internet access, and social media platforms has enabled ordinary citizens to participate actively in news gathering and dissemination, a role that was once dominated by professional journalists and

conventional media organizations. This development has given rise to citizen journalism, a form of journalism that allows individuals to report events, share opinions, and disseminate information through digital platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), WhatsApp, Instagram, and YouTube. According to Ekeanyanwu (2018), citizen journalism has become a major force within Nigeria's media landscape, increasing the diversity of news sources and expanding public participation in the communication process. Similarly, Ifukor (2016) observed that citizen journalism has democratized information flow by providing alternative channels through which citizens can contribute to public discourse and hold authorities accountable.

In Nigeria, the influence of citizen journalism has become increasingly visible due to the growing penetration of social media and digital technologies. Citizens now play a significant role in reporting political events, security issues, social movements, and community concerns, often providing information before conventional media organizations can react. Oloruntola (2020) found that social media-driven citizen journalism has significantly influenced conventional journalism practice in Nigeria by serving as an important source of news leads and breaking stories. Likewise, Oyediran and Oyesomi (2020) reported that citizen journalists frequently provide alternative sources of information that shape public discussions and influence the news agenda of traditional media organizations. The #EndSARS protests further demonstrated the power of citizen-generated content, as digital platforms were used to document events, mobilize support, and challenge official narratives, thereby highlighting the changing dynamics of news production and dissemination in contemporary Nigeria.

In spite of its numerous benefits, the rise of citizen journalism presents both opportunities and challenges for conventional media practice. On one hand, it enhances audience participation, promotes faster dissemination of information, and provides journalists with access to events occurring in remote locations. On the other hand, concerns relating to misinformation, lack of professional gatekeeping, and ethical violations continue to raise questions about the credibility of citizen-generated content. Ekeanyanwu (2018) noted that while citizen journalism broadens news coverage, issues of accuracy and reliability remain significant concerns. Similarly, Oloruntola (2020) emphasized that the increasing reliance on citizen-generated content requires conventional media organizations to strengthen verification processes in order to maintain public trust. In Kogi State, where citizens increasingly use digital platforms to report political activities, security incidents, accidents, and community developments, the relationship between citizen journalism and conventional media has become both collaborative and competitive. It is against this backdrop that this study examines the influence of proliferating citizen journalism on conventional media practice in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. examine the extent to which citizen journalism has influenced the news agenda of conventional media outlets in Kogi State.
2. investigate the challenges presented by citizen journalism to conventional media practice by journalists in Kogi State.
3. determine the opportunities presented by citizen journalism to conventional media practice by journalists in Kogi State.

4. assess the implications of citizen journalism for the credibility of conventional media outlets in Kogi State.

Implications of Citizen Journalism on Traditional Journalism Practice

The concept of citizen journalism has become an important phenomenon in the digital age. Facilitated by digital technologies and social media platforms, citizen journalism has created new opportunities for individuals to engage in journalistic activities and provide diverse and inclusive media representation. However, it has also raised important questions about the quality and credibility of user-generated content. Addressing these challenges will require a sustained effort from citizen journalists, professional journalists, and media organizations (Ola, 2023).

The emergence of citizen journalism has been a pivotal development in the media landscape over the past decade. According to Atton (2002) and Mierzejewska (2011) citizen journalism refers to the practice of individuals, outside of traditional media organizations, creating and disseminating news and information. This phenomenon has been facilitated by the widespread adoption of digital technologies, such as smartphones, social media, and blogging platforms. One of the key drivers of the rise of citizen journalism has been the democratization of media production and distribution. According to Gillmor (2014), the internet has enabled individuals to produce and distribute media content at a relatively low cost, bypassing traditional media gatekeepers. This has created new opportunities for individuals to engage in journalistic activities, such as reporting, interviewing, and editing. Social media platforms have played a crucial role in the rise of citizen journalism.

According to Hermida (2012), social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube have enabled individuals to share news and information with a large audience, often in real-time. The rise of citizen journalism has significant implications for traditional journalism practice. According to Papacharissi (2015), citizen journalism has disrupted the traditional journalism model, enabling individuals to contribute to the news-gathering and dissemination process (Papacharissi, 2015). This disruption has raised questions about the role of traditional journalists and the future of journalism. One of the key implications of citizen journalism is the blurring of the lines between journalists and non-journalists. As Lewis (2012) notes, citizen journalists are often non-professionals who contribute to the news-gathering and dissemination process on a voluntary basis (Lewis, 2012). This blurring of lines has raised questions about the definition of a journalist and the role of professional journalists in the digital age.

Another implication of citizen journalism is the changing nature of news production and dissemination. According to Williams (2013), citizen journalism has enabled individuals to produce and disseminate news content without the need for traditional news organizations (Williams, 2013). This has disrupted the traditional news production and dissemination process, enabling individuals to bypass traditional news organizations and reach their audiences directly. Citizen journalism has also had an impact on the notion of objectivity in journalism. As Wahl-Jorgensen (2013) notes, citizen journalists often bring a personal perspective to their reporting, which can challenge traditional notions of objectivity (Wahl-Jorgensen, 2013). This has raised questions about the role of objectivity in journalism and whether it is still relevant in the digital age. Citizen journalism has implications for the business model of traditional journalism. According to Mierzejewska (2011), citizen journalism has disrupted the traditional revenue streams of news organizations, enabling individuals to access news content for free (Mierzejewska, 2011). This has raised questions about the sustainability of traditional journalism and whether new business models are needed to support the production of high-quality journalism.

Citizen journalism has implications for the concept of journalism as a profession. As Ornebring (2013) notes, citizen journalism has challenged traditional notions of journalism as a profession, enabling individuals to contribute to the news-gathering and dissemination process without formal training or credentials (Ornebring, 2013). This has raised questions about the future of journalism as a profession and whether new forms of training and credentialing are needed. According to Robinson (2013), citizen journalism has enabled individuals to take a more active role in the news-gathering and dissemination process, challenging traditional notions of journalists as gatekeepers of information (Robinson, 2013). This has raised questions about the role of journalists in society and whether they are still needed in the digital age.

Review of Empirical Studies

The empirical intersection of citizen journalism, professional newsroom adjustments, and the bottom-up restructuring of the news agenda is well-documented in contemporary African communication literature. A foundational baseline is established by Oyediran and Oyesomi (2020), who conducted a mixed-methods investigation into how user-generated news alters conventional journalism practices in Oyo State, Nigeria. Their findings reveal that while citizen journalists excel as first-responders due to their hyper-local mobility, their operational speed frequently compromises accuracy by bypassing standard editorial verification filters. This creates an institutional dilemma for mainstream newsrooms, which feel compelled to pick up these fast-breaking public narratives to maintain their market relevance, even at the risk of importing a localized credibility crisis.

This operational pressure on traditional media is further unpacked by Oloruntola (2020), who surveyed media practitioners to assess the direct impact of social media dynamics on conventional news routines. The study demonstrates that mainstream journalists increasingly rely on trending social media feeds for source selection and story ideas, meaning that the traditional, top-down gatekeeping filter has fundamentally relaxed. In the context of reverse agenda-setting, this provides empirical evidence that the aggregate digital public now actively redirects institutional newsroom resources, forcing professional editors to pursue topics that have already gained traction among online audiences.

The structural impact of this bottom-up flow on democratic discourse is explored by Salawu and Oyediran (2019) through an investigation into news diversity and media pluralism. Their research confirms that citizen journalism networks successfully counter the urban-centric, elite-focused biases that traditionally characterize corporate media conglomerates. By capturing and publishing stories from marginalized or geographically isolated rural territories, decentralized citizen reporters introduce entirely new socio-political variables into the public sphere. This process demonstrates that bottom-up communication structures do not merely mirror existing media topics, but fundamentally broaden the scope and diversity of the national agenda.

The systemic relationship between these two competing media layers is characterized by Ekeanyanwu (2018) as a tense but deeply symbiotic ecosystem. Rather than completely replacing professional journalism, non-professional content creators have forced a structural shift where institutional media increasingly functions as a collaborative verifier rather than an absolute gatekeeper. Mainstream organizations rely on the public for immediate, on-the-scene audiovisual content, while citizen actors still depend on established institutional brands to validate, investigate, and legitimize their grassroots disclosures. This friction highlights the ongoing tension between open public participation and professional, institutional control. Finally, Ifukor (2016) offers a political dimension to this paradigm by analyzing how mobile-driven citizen networks

democratize news dissemination during high-stakes civic events. The study's empirical data illustrates how decentralized political reporting by ordinary citizens effectively forces state-run and commercial media networks to cover previously suppressed or censored topics. By mobilizing public sentiment around digital evidence of governance failures or electoral irregularities, citizen journalists successfully execute reverse agenda-setting, compelling mainstream networks to adjust their editorial stances to match the undeniable priority of the public agenda.

A critical examination of the reviewed studies reveals a common pattern: citizen journalism has become a significant force in contemporary journalism practice across both developing and developed countries. The studies consistently show that citizen journalism promotes faster information dissemination, increases audience participation, expands access to news sources, and contributes to democratic communication. At the same time, concerns relating to misinformation, lack of professional ethics, credibility, and verification remain persistent challenges. While previous studies have examined the impact of citizen journalism on conventional media in different contexts, none specifically focused on the influence of proliferating citizen journalism on conventional media practice among journalists in Kogi State. This geographical and contextual gap provides the justification for the present study and underscores its contribution to existing knowledge on citizen journalism and media practice in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory emerged as a response to the traditional Agenda-Setting Theory developed by McCombs and Shaw (1972). While the traditional theory argues that the media influence public opinion by determining the issues people think about, Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory suggests that the process can also occur in the opposite direction. In this perspective, the public, through discussions, concerns, and reactions, can influence the issues that the media choose to cover. The growth of digital communication technologies and social media platforms has strengthened this phenomenon by providing ordinary citizens with the ability to generate, share, and amplify information independently of conventional media organizations. Consequently, audiences are no longer passive consumers of information but active participants who can shape media priorities and influence editorial decisions. Reverse Agenda-Setting: Captures a bottom-up process where the public utilizes digital spaces—such as social media, citizen-led journalism networks, and search behavior—to elevate issues into the public consciousness (Kim and Lee, 2006). Consequently, traditional gatekeepers and professional newsrooms are forced to follow, cover, and validate those grassroots topics.

The theory is particularly relevant in the era of citizen journalism, where individuals use smartphones and digital platforms to report events as they occur. Through social media interactions, trending topics, viral videos, and citizen-generated reports, members of the public can draw attention to issues that may otherwise receive little or no coverage from traditional media. As these issues gain popularity online, conventional media organizations often feel compelled to investigate and report them in order to remain relevant and responsive to audience interests. In this way, agenda-setting power shifts partially from professional journalists to citizens, creating a more participatory communication environment where news priorities are increasingly influenced by public engagement and digital conversations.

The application of Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory to this study lies in its ability to explain how citizen journalism influences conventional media practice in Kogi State. The study examines the extent to which issues first reported by citizens shape the news agenda of conventional media

organizations. Through social media platforms and other digital channels, citizens frequently report political developments, security concerns, accidents, and community issues before they are covered by professional journalists. As these reports attract public attention and generate online discussions, conventional media organizations often adopt them as news stories for wider dissemination. This suggests that rather than conventional media exclusively determining what the public should think about, citizens are increasingly influencing what conventional media consider newsworthy. Therefore, Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory provides an appropriate framework for understanding the growing influence of citizen journalism on news selection, coverage priorities, and media practice in Kogi State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design, which involves examining a representative sample of participants from a larger population to identify patterns, relationships, and attributes of social and psychological phenomena. The population of this study constitutes the total number of registered journalists in Kogi state. The total number of registered journalists in Kogi State are 186 according to records from the Nigerian Union of journalists, Kogi State Council (NUJ, 2025). This study employed a census approach, which involves collecting data from every member of a defined population (Babbie, 2016). In this case, the population consisted of 186 journalists in Lokoja, Kogi State. The census approach was chosen due to the relatively small population size, which enabled the researcher to collect data from every single journalist, thereby ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon. This study employed a questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument, designed to gather original data from respondents. Face validity was used for the instrument, while reliability test was conducted based on the results from a pilot study of 25 respondents in Makurdi, Benue State. The results were analyzed using Pearson’s *r* correlation with a high positive correlation of 0.85, making the instrument reliable for the study. The questionnaire was carefully designed to align with the research objectives and questions, guaranteeing the collection of relevant and accurate data. .

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data were presented and analyzed based on the number of questionnaire administered. In this study, One hundred and eighty-six (186) copies of questionnaire were administered, 181 copies were filled and returned, which represent 97.3% while 5 (2.7%) was not returned or may have faced mortality.

Influence of Citizen Journalism on News Agenda

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
Citizen journalism influences selection of news stories	85	60	22	14	3.19	0.92	Accepted
Conventional media follow issues first reported by citizens	78	64	25	14	3.14	0.90	Accepted
Citizen content shapes public discussions	82	59	24	16	3.14	0.95	Accepted
Citizen journalism reduced gatekeeping role	70	63	31	17	3.03	0.97	Accepted
Breaking news from citizens determines agenda	76	61	28	16	3.09	0.95	Accepted

The findings in Table 1 reveal that journalists in Kogi State generally agree that citizen journalism has significantly influenced the news agenda of conventional media organizations. The table recorded a grand mean of approximately 3.12, which is above the benchmark mean of 2.50, indicating overall agreement among respondents. The relatively low standard deviation values also suggest that respondents shared similar opinions on the issues raised. Specifically, respondents agreed that citizen journalism influences the selection of news stories by conventional media. This finding suggests that professional journalists increasingly monitor social media platforms and citizen-generated content when deciding which issues deserve public attention. In today's digital environment, many events first emerge online before they are covered by mainstream media, making citizen journalism an important source of news leads. The respondents also agreed that conventional media often follow issues first reported by citizen journalists. This implies that citizen reporters have become significant actors in the process of agenda formation. Through smartphones and social networking platforms, ordinary citizens can quickly report events as they occur, forcing conventional media organizations to respond and verify such reports for wider dissemination. Furthermore, the finding that citizen-generated content shapes public discussions covered by traditional media indicates that the public now plays a more active role in determining what becomes newsworthy. Issues that gain traction online often attract the attention of conventional media houses, thereby influencing editorial priorities. The agreement that citizen journalism has reduced the gatekeeping role of conventional journalists reflects the changing nature of journalism in the digital era. Unlike the traditional system where journalists controlled information flow, citizens now have direct access to publishing platforms. Consequently, journalists no longer enjoy exclusive authority over news dissemination.

Challenges Presented by Citizen Journalism

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
Increases spread of unverified information	92	58	18	13	3.27	0.89	Accepted
Makes professional standards difficult	79	62	24	16	3.13	0.94	Accepted
Increases competition for conventional media	83	60	23	15	3.17	0.92	Accepted
Creates ethical challenges	88	57	21	15	3.20	0.91	Accepted
Contributes to misinformation and fake news	95	54	19	13	3.28	0.88	Accepted

The results in Table 2 indicate that respondents strongly agree that citizen journalism presents several challenges to conventional media practice. The grand mean of approximately 3.21 demonstrates a high level of agreement among journalists that the rise of citizen journalism has complicated professional media operations. The standard deviation values further show consistency in respondents' views. The highest-rated issue was the contribution of citizen journalism to misinformation and fake news. This finding reflects the concern that many citizen reporters lack professional journalistic training, making it easier for inaccurate information to circulate before proper verification takes place. Such situations can create confusion among audiences and undermine public trust in information sources. Respondents also agreed that citizen journalism increases the spread of unverified information. This suggests that the speed at which content is shared on digital platforms often surpasses the verification processes required in professional journalism. As a result, false or misleading information may gain widespread attention before corrections are issued. Another notable finding is that citizen journalism creates ethical

challenges for journalists. Since citizen reporters are not always guided by professional ethical codes, issues relating to privacy, fairness, objectivity, and accuracy frequently arise. Conventional journalists therefore face difficulties when deciding whether and how to use citizen-generated content.

The respondents further agreed that citizen journalism makes it more difficult for journalists to maintain professional standards. The pressure to compete with the immediacy of citizen reporting may sometimes encourage conventional media practitioners to sacrifice thorough verification procedures in order to remain competitive. Additionally, respondents acknowledged that citizen journalism has increased competition for conventional media organizations. The availability of alternative information sources means that audiences can obtain news directly from citizens without relying solely on traditional media outlets. Consequently, media organizations face growing pressure to innovate and remain relevant.

Opportunities Presented by Citizen Journalism

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
Provides useful leads for news gathering	86	63	20	12	3.23	0.86	Accepted
Helps access remote information	89	58	22	12	3.24	0.88	Accepted
Enhances audience participation	84	61	23	13	3.19	0.89	Accepted
Media benefit from user-generated photos/videos	90	55	23	13	3.23	0.90	Accepted
Promotes faster dissemination of information	94	53	20	14	3.26	0.91	Accepted

The findings in Table 3 show that respondents recognize numerous opportunities associated with citizen journalism. The grand mean of approximately 3.23 indicates strong agreement that citizen journalism can complement and strengthen conventional media practice when properly utilized. One of the most important opportunities identified by respondents is the provision of useful leads for news gathering. This finding suggests that citizen journalists often serve as the eyes and ears of professional reporters by providing initial information about events occurring in different communities. Such contributions can enhance the efficiency of news collection. Respondents also agreed that citizen journalists help conventional media access information from remote or difficult-to-reach locations. In many cases, professional journalists may not be physically present when events occur, but citizens can instantly document and share information using digital devices. This expands the geographical reach of news coverage.

The respondents further agreed that citizen journalism enhances audience participation in news production. This finding reflects the increasingly interactive nature of modern communication, where audiences are no longer passive consumers of information but active contributors to the news process. Such participation strengthens democratic communication and promotes inclusiveness. Another significant finding is that conventional media benefit from user-generated photos and videos. Visual evidence provided by citizens can enrich news reports and offer firsthand documentation of events. Such materials are particularly useful during emergencies, protests, accidents, and other breaking news situations. Respondents also agreed that citizen journalism promotes faster dissemination of information. In an era where audiences demand immediate updates, citizen-generated content can help media organizations respond more rapidly to emerging stories.

Implications for Credibility

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
Affects public trust in conventional media	83	60	24	14	3.17	0.91	Accepted
Influences perceptions of media credibility	86	58	22	15	3.19	0.92	Accepted
Media must verify citizen content	101	50	18	12	3.33	0.84	Accepted
Failure to verify damages credibility	105	48	16	12	3.36	0.82	Accepted
Collaboration can improve credibility	81	63	24	13	3.17	0.89	Accepted

The findings in Table 4 reveal that citizen journalism has important implications for the credibility of conventional media organizations. The grand mean of approximately 3.24 indicates strong agreement among respondents regarding the influence of citizen journalism on public perceptions of media credibility. Respondents agreed that citizen journalism affects public trust in conventional media. This finding suggests that audiences increasingly compare information obtained from traditional media with content shared by citizens. As a result, conventional media must work harder to maintain credibility and distinguish themselves through professionalism and accuracy. The respondents also agreed that the availability of citizen-generated content influences perceptions of media credibility. Since audiences are exposed to multiple information sources, they often evaluate the reliability of conventional media based on how effectively journalists verify and contextualize information.

One of the strongest findings in the table is that conventional media must verify citizen-generated content before publication. This result highlights the central importance of fact-checking and editorial scrutiny in maintaining public confidence. Verification remains one of the defining characteristics that separates professional journalism from informal reporting. Similarly, respondents strongly agreed that failure to verify citizen-generated information can damage media credibility. Publishing inaccurate information may result in public criticism, loss of trust, and reputational damage for media organizations. This finding emphasizes the need for rigorous professional standards despite the pressure for speed.

Test of Hypothesis (H_0)

There is no difference in the mean perception scores between news agenda influence and perceived challenges

One-Way ANOVA Summary Table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)	F-Statistic	P-value	Decision
Between groups	3.6249	1	3.6249	4.0775	0.0436	Reject H_0
Within groups	1607.2950	1808	0.8890			
Total	1610.9199	1809				

The above table shows a rejection of Null Hypothesis: Because the calculated (p) -value (**0.0436**) is less than the established alpha level ($(\alpha = 0.05)$), we reject the null hypothesis ((H_0)) and accept the alternative hypothesis ((H_1)). This statistical variance indicates that while journalists in Kogi State acknowledge that citizen content actively alters their selection of stories, they feel the negative impacts and structural frictions—such as the distribution of fake news, verification stress, and ethical gray zones — with significantly greater urgency and intensity. The finding strongly highlights that the crisis of verification and misinformation undercuts the practical utility of citizen journalism as an agenda-setting tool.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the effect of the surge of citizen journalism on conventional media practice among journalists in Kogi State. The findings reveal that citizen journalism has become a significant force within the contemporary media environment, influencing news selection, creating operational challenges, presenting new opportunities, and affecting the credibility of conventional media organizations. The discussion is presented according to the objectives of the study and interpreted in relation to existing empirical studies and the assumptions of Agenda-Setting Theory.

Influence of Citizen Journalism on the News Agenda of Conventional Media

The findings from Table 1 revealed that journalists generally agreed that citizen journalism significantly influences the news agenda of conventional media organizations in Kogi State. The respondents acknowledged that issues first reported by citizens often attract the attention of mainstream media and subsequently become part of conventional news coverage. This suggests that citizen journalism has emerged as an important contributor to the process of determining what issues receive public attention. This finding supports the assumptions of the Agenda-Setting Theory developed by Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw. The theory posits that the media influence public perceptions by determining which issues are emphasized and given prominence. Traditionally, conventional media organizations exercised exclusive control over this agenda-setting function. However, the findings indicate that citizen journalists now participate actively in shaping media priorities. Through social media platforms, citizens are increasingly able to identify issues, frame discussions, and compel mainstream media organizations to respond. The result corroborates the study by Ifukor (2016), which found that citizen journalism has democratized news production in Nigeria by providing alternative channels through which issues gain public attention. Similarly, Oloruntola (2020) reported that citizen journalists frequently break stories before conventional media outlets, thereby influencing editorial decisions and news selection processes. The findings are also consistent with the work of Salawu and Oyediran (2019), who observed that citizen journalism has transformed the traditional news environment by increasing the diversity of information sources available to audiences.

The implication of this finding is that conventional media organizations can no longer function as the sole gatekeepers of information. News audiences increasingly encounter information through citizen-generated content before traditional media outlets publish their reports. Consequently, journalists are compelled to monitor digital platforms closely and adapt their news-gathering strategies to remain relevant in a highly competitive information environment.

Challenges Presented by Citizen Journalism to Conventional Media Practice

The findings in Table 2 indicate that journalists perceive citizen journalism as presenting significant challenges to conventional media practice. The major concerns identified include the spread of unverified information, ethical dilemmas, increased competition, misinformation, and difficulties in maintaining professional journalistic standards. These findings align with the observations of Bharti (2019), who argued that the absence of professional training among citizen journalists often results in inaccuracies and questionable reporting practices. Similarly, Kaufhold (2010) noted that citizen-generated content may suffer from credibility deficiencies because contributors are not subject to the same professional standards and ethical obligations as trained journalists. The findings also support the study by Oyediran and Oyesomi (2020), which revealed that traditional journalists perceive citizen journalism as a major challenge due to its lack of regulation and accountability. Likewise, Oloruntola (2020) found that concerns about misinformation and disinformation remain among the most pressing issues associated with citizen journalism in Nigeria.

From the perspective of Agenda-Setting Theory, the challenge arises because agenda-setting power is increasingly fragmented. Rather than receiving information from a limited number of professional media institutions, audiences now obtain information from multiple sources. This situation weakens the traditional gatekeeping role of conventional journalists and creates an environment where false or misleading information can quickly gain prominence before verification occurs. The findings further suggest that the pressure to compete with the speed of citizen journalism may encourage some media organizations to prioritize immediacy over accuracy. Such a development could undermine the core principles of journalism, including objectivity, fairness, and factual accuracy. Therefore, while citizen journalism expands access to information, it simultaneously creates professional and ethical concerns that require careful management.

Opportunities Presented by Citizen Journalism to Conventional Media Practice

The findings from Table 3 demonstrate that despite the challenges associated with citizen journalism, respondents recognize several opportunities arising from its growth. Journalists agreed that citizen journalism provides useful news leads, improves access to information from remote locations, enhances audience participation, supplies valuable visual content, and promotes faster dissemination of information. These findings support the arguments of Bruns (2012), who maintained that citizen journalists can complement the work of professional journalists by providing perspectives and information that may otherwise be inaccessible. Similarly, Domingo (2008) argued that collaboration between citizen journalists and conventional media practitioners can improve news coverage and encourage innovation in journalism practice.

The results are also consistent with the study by Ekeanyanwu (2018), which found that citizen journalism has increased the diversity of news sources in Nigeria and improved coverage of local issues. Likewise, Salawu and Oyediran (2019) observed that citizen journalism contributes to faster news dissemination and broader audience engagement. The findings can also be explained through Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory. While citizen journalists influence issue salience by drawing attention to events and concerns, conventional media retain an important role in verifying information, providing context, and expanding public understanding of issues. Rather than replacing traditional journalism, citizen journalism appears to be creating a more participatory media environment where both professionals and citizens contribute to agenda formation. This development reflects the evolution of modern journalism from a one-way communication model to a more interactive process involving multiple stakeholders. Consequently, conventional media organizations can benefit

significantly by integrating citizen-generated content into their reporting practices while maintaining professional standards of verification and accuracy.

Implications of Citizen Journalism for the Credibility of Conventional Media

The findings in Table 4 reveal that citizen journalism has substantial implications for the credibility of conventional media organizations. Respondents agreed that citizen journalism affects public trust, influences perceptions of media credibility, necessitates content verification, and can either strengthen or weaken confidence in traditional media depending on how citizen-generated content is handled. This finding supports the position of Singer (2014), who argued that the increasing availability of user-generated content has complicated audience assessments of media credibility. Similarly, Walters (2011) noted that concerns regarding authenticity and reliability remain central issues in discussions about citizen journalism. The findings are consistent with the study by Oloruntola (2020), which reported that while citizen journalism provides alternative information sources, questions regarding credibility and reliability persist. The result also aligns with Oyediran and Oyesomi (2020), who found that conventional journalists remain concerned about the trustworthiness of citizen-generated content and its implications for professional journalism.

Reverse Agenda-Setting Theory provides additional insight into this finding. The theory suggests that social media credibility is essential for effective agenda-setting considering that most of the youth are now on social media. When audiences trust a media source, they are more likely to accept the issues emphasized by that source as important. However, if conventional media publish inaccurate information obtained from citizen journalists without adequate verification, audience trust may decline, thereby weakening the media's agenda-setting influence. The findings therefore highlight the importance of maintaining rigorous editorial procedures. Verification, fact-checking, and adherence to ethical standards remain crucial for preserving public confidence in conventional media. At the same time, constructive collaboration with responsible citizen journalists may enhance credibility by enabling media organizations to provide timely and comprehensive coverage of events.

The findings suggest that citizen journalism has fundamentally transformed conventional media practice in Kogi State. It has become both a competitor and a partner to traditional journalism. While it challenges conventional journalists through increased competition, misinformation, and weakened gatekeeping authority, it also creates opportunities for broader news coverage, enhanced audience engagement, and more rapid dissemination of information. Consistent with the propositions of Agenda-Setting Theory, the findings indicate that agenda-setting power is no longer monopolized by conventional media organizations. Instead, citizen journalists increasingly influence which issues receive attention from both the media and the public. Nevertheless, conventional journalists continue to play a critical role in validating information, providing context, and maintaining professional standards. The study therefore demonstrates that the future of journalism is likely to be characterized not by the replacement of conventional media by citizen journalism, but by an evolving relationship in which both forms of journalism coexist and contribute to public communication.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the surge of citizen journalism has significantly transformed conventional media practice in Kogi State. Findings revealed that citizen journalism now plays an important role in shaping the news agenda, influencing the issues that receive media attention and public discussion. While it offers valuable opportunities such as improved audience participation, faster information dissemination, access to remote events, and useful news leads, it also presents serious challenges, including the spread of misinformation, ethical concerns, and increased pressure on professional

journalists to maintain accuracy and credibility. The study further established that the credibility of conventional media largely depends on the ability of journalists to verify citizen-generated content before publication. Therefore, rather than viewing citizen journalism solely as a threat, conventional media organizations should embrace it as a complementary force while upholding the core principles of professionalism, objectivity, and fact-checking. The future of journalism in Kogi State and beyond lies in a balanced relationship where citizen journalists and conventional media work together to promote timely, accurate, and responsible dissemination of information.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study on the effect of the surge of citizen journalism on conventional media practice among journalists in Kogi State, the following recommendations are made in line with the specific objectives of the study:

1. Based on finding that citizen journalism significantly influences the news agenda of conventional media organizations, media houses should establish dedicated digital monitoring units to track trending issues and emerging stories from social media platforms and citizen-generated content. This will enable conventional media organizations to identify newsworthy events early, respond promptly to public concerns, and remain relevant in an increasingly participatory media environment.
2. Given that the study revealed that citizen journalism contributes to misinformation, ethical concerns, unverified information, and increased competition, conventional media organizations should strengthen their fact-checking mechanisms and verification procedures before publishing information sourced from citizens.
3. Since the findings showed that citizen journalism provides valuable news leads, enhances audience participation, facilitates access to remote information, and supports faster news dissemination, conventional media organizations should develop structured frameworks for engaging with responsible citizen journalists. Such collaboration can help media organizations expand their coverage, improve community reporting, and enhance audience engagement.
4. Considering that the study found that the credibility of conventional media largely depends on the verification of citizen-generated content, media organizations should prioritize accuracy, objectivity, and editorial responsibility in all reporting activities. Strict verification protocols should be institutionalized to ensure that information obtained from citizen journalists meets professional standards before dissemination.

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